

Design of the Spherical Actuated Proximal Joint of a 4-DoA Robotic Extra-Finger

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Abstract—The paper presents the design of a wearable supernumerary finger for human hand augmentation and compensation. The proposed device presents an actuated, 3-DoF proximal joint, controlling finger orientation, and a tendon-driven mechanism for realizing the flexion/extension motion. The proximal spherical joint is realized by means of a compact spherical 3-RRR parallel mechanism. The device is actuated by four actuators, placed on its base fixed on the user's forearm. The overall device has a size and weight comparable with the one with a single actuator developed in previous studies, but increased manipulability and dexterity performance. The paper illustrates the proposed device design and control, focusing in particular on the proximal 3-DoF spherical joint.

Index Terms—Human augmentation, wearable extra fingers, wearable robots.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human augmentation through supernumerary limbs is a recent but rather active research topic involving different and multidisciplinary aspects, ranging from mechatronic design and control, up to the impact on neuroscientific, psychological, and ethical impact on humans [1], [2], [3]. Besides the challenging aspect related to human augmentation and to all the related research questions, this type of device has also a more immediate application to people with reduced hand motion capabilities (e.g. stroke patients [4], [5]).

Our research group has focused in the last decade on human hand augmentation by means of supernumerary robotic fingers. Different solutions have been proposed: the first prototypes of supernumerary fingers were rather bulky and fully actuated [6], [7], and were used to test some preliminary ideas about how extra robotic limbs can coordinate with the human body [8]. The need for lighter and more portable solutions, especially for daily use by people with reduced hand and arm mobility, led to the development of simpler, lighter, and more robust solutions with a limited number of actuators [9]. Solutions with multiple fingers coordinated by a differential mechanism were also proposed [10].

In this work, we present a new version of the robotic extra finger with enhanced mobility and dexterity, obtained

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Fig. 1: The 4-DoA robotic extra finger. The proximal joint is realized by a 3-DoF, spherical 3-RRR mechanism, the following flexible part is composed of a series of seven soft modules and is driven by a tendon.

by substituting the proximal joint with a 3-DoF spherical 3-RRR parallel mechanism (Fig. 1). The spherical mechanism is rather light and compact, so it keeps a suitable wearability. The enhanced proximal joint allows the extension of the range of possible motions that the finger can perform: besides flexion/extension, adduction/abduction and rotation motions are possible. In this way, the device workspace is significantly increased, and more complex hand/extra-finger coordinated motions can be realized. The device will be used to investigate research problems related to human augmentation with robotic extra limbs [11]. In this paper in particular we will focus on the design and control of the 3-DoF proximal joint.

II. DEVICE DESCRIPTION

A. Finger structure

As mentioned in the previous section, in this work we improved the wearable extra finger developed in [9], [12] to provide more DoF and enrich the set of possible motions. The starting point of the proposed device is the robotic extra finger described in [9], which has a modular structure, where each module is composed of a rigid part realized in ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene, ABSPlus, Stratasys, USA) and flexible part, made of TPU (thermoplastic polyurethane, Lulzbot, USA). TPU was selected in particular because the high elongation of this material allows for repeated movement and impact without wear or fatigue phenomena. The modular structure allows the addition or removal of phalanges to customize finger length, the stiffness of the flexible elements can be regulated in the manufacturing phase to customize finger closure movement [9]. In this paper, seven modules

Fig. 2: The 3-DoF, 3-RRR spherical parallel mechanism for proximal joint actuation: 3D-CAD model and prototype

were employed in order to achieve a length of the finger so that the device can reach the fingertips in the extended configuration of an average adult human hand. The robotic extra finger is tendon-driven and is actuated by only one motor, providing the flexion movement. The extension motion is passively obtained when the tendon is released by means of the elastic interphalangeal elements. Motion capabilities of this device are limited to finger flexion/extension only. Neglecting passive uncontrollable deformation of interphalangeal elastic elements, the fingertip trajectory is limited to a plane.

To obtain a wider set of movements and to increase the device workspace, a compact spherical parallel mechanism has been introduced in the proximal joint, connecting the finger to the forearm support.

B. 3-DoF parallel mechanism for proximal joint actuation

The proposed mechanism for realizing the proximal joint is a 3-DoF, 3-RRR parallel structure where R-joint axes intersect at a common point, namely the center of the sphere. In this type of parallel mechanism, the mobile platform has a spherical 3-DoF motion with respect to the base. The joint has 3 motors on the base (Dynamixel XL330-M077-T), actuating the proximal R joints. In the proposed implementation, such axes are parallel. The direct and inverse kinematic model of such a mechanism is presented in [13]. The parallel mechanism configuration is controlled by measuring the relative orientation between its mobile part and the base by means of two Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) InvenSense MPU92504. An OpenCM 9.04 C-Type microcontroller is used to elaborate IMU measures and control the actuators. The mechanism structure is manufactured with an FDM process using ABS material.

III. DEVICE MODEL AND CONTROL

The proposed device has 4 Degrees of Actuation (DoA), 3 of them are used to control finger proximal joint configuration, and the fourth controls finger flexion and extension movements.

This last part of the movement is not detailed in this paper, since it is an update of the solutions presented in previous

Fig. 3: Kinematic scheme of the 3-DoF, 3-RRR parallel mechanism.

works. The main contribution of this paper is represented by the spherical joint and in the following we focus on it.

According to the notation suggested in [13], and the scheme shown in Fig. 3, let us indicate with \mathbf{u}_i , \mathbf{w}_i , \mathbf{v}_i , with $i = 1, \dots, 3$, the unit vectors corresponding to the directions of the proximal, intermediate and distal R-joints, respectively. The components of such unit vectors are represented w.r.t. a base reference frame $\mathcal{S}_0 = \{O_0, x_0, y_0, z_0\}$ whose origin O_0 is in the center of the sphere. Since distal R-joints are located on the mobile part of the parallel mechanism, the spherical joint configuration can be related to \mathbf{v}_i by means of straightforward kinematic relationships.

We indicate with α_1 the angle between proximal and intermediate R-joints (i.e., between \mathbf{u}_i and \mathbf{w}_i unit vectors) and with α_2 the angle between the intermediate and distal R-joints (i.e., between \mathbf{w}_i and \mathbf{v}_i unit vectors). Assuming that such angles are the same for the three legs, the inverse kinematics problem can be formulated as three quadratic equations [14]:

$$A_i T_i^2 + B_i T_i + C_i = 0, \quad (1)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} T_i &= \tan(\theta_i/2), \\ A_i &= -v_{iy} \sin \alpha_1 - v_{iz} \cos \alpha_1 - \cos \alpha_2, \\ B_i &= v_{ix} \sin \alpha_1, \\ C_i &= v_{iy} \sin \alpha_1 - v_{iz} \cos \alpha_1 - \cos \alpha_2, \end{aligned}$$

where v_{ix}, v_{iy}, v_{iz} are the components of unit vectors \mathbf{v}_i w.r.t. the base reference frame \mathcal{S}_0 .

The orientation of the mobile platform of the spherical mechanism w.r.t. the base is measured by means of two Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) \mathcal{I}_0 and \mathcal{I}_1 , located on the base and the mobile platform of the spherical mechanism,

Fig. 4: Block diagram of the spherical mechanism orientation control system.

respectively, whose outputs are two quaternions \mathbf{q}^0 and \mathbf{q}^1 , both expressed w.r.t. an external inertial reference frame. The relative orientation between the base and mobile platform can be expressed by means of the following quaternion:

$$\mathbf{q}_1^0 = \mathbf{q}^1 \times (\mathbf{q}^0)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Standard kinematic relationships can be therefore used to transform mobile platform orientation expressed by the quaternion \mathbf{q}_1^0 into Euler parameters and then the unit vectors \mathbf{v}_i can be evaluated.

The orientation control system for the spherical joint takes as input the desired orientation expressed in terms of quaternion as \mathbf{q}_{1des}^0 . The inverse kinematics algorithm transforms it in the actuator space θ_{des} . The actual orientation \mathbf{q}_1^0 is measured by the IMU sensors as described above and is transformed in actuator rotation angles θ with the above-mentioned inverse kinematics algorithm. A standard PID controller is used to generate the input for the actuators. A block diagram of the proposed control system is reported in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 reports the results of two tests where the target orientation of the platform was randomly changed with a step function. The orientation position control is able to follow the desired reference orientation with suitable dynamic performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

The aim of this work is to propose a new version of a supernumerary robotic finger with enhanced dexterity and mobility performance with respect to the solutions previously developed by our research group, still maintaining suitable levels of wearability, robustness, and user comfort. The solution that has been developed is based on the integration of the finger with a compact actuated 3-DoF spherical mechanism in the proximal joint. In the paper, kinematics, design, and control of the mechanism are summarized. The whole prototype of the finger and its first functional tests will be ready within 2023.

REFERENCES

[1] D. Prattichizzo, M. Pozzi, T. L. Baldi, M. Malvezzi, I. Hussain, S. Rossi, and G. Salvietti, "Human augmentation by wearable supernumerary robotic limbs: review and perspectives," *Progress in Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 4, p. 042005, 2021.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Platform rotation angles ϕ , θ , ψ (expressed as Euler's angles) and actuator rotation angles θ_1 , θ_2 , θ_3 in two tests where the reference orientation was varied with a step function with randomized reference values.

[2] Y. Tong and J. Liu, "Review of research and development of supernumerary robotic limbs," *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 929–952, 2021.

[3] B. Yang, J. Huang, X. Chen, C. Xiong, and Y. Hasegawa, "Supernumerary robotic limbs: A review and future outlook," *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 623–639, 2021.

[4] I. Hussain, G. Salvietti, G. Spagnoletti, M. Malvezzi, D. Cioncoloni, S. Rossi, and D. Prattichizzo, "A soft supernumerary robotic finger and mobile arm support for grasping compensation and hemiparetic upper limb rehabilitation," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 93, pp. 1–12, 2017.

[5] D. Prattichizzo, M. Malvezzi, and G. Salvietti, "Supernumerary robotic fingers to compensate and augment human manipulation abilities," in *Inclusive Robotics for a Better Society: Selected Papers from INBOTS Conference 2018, 16-18 October, 2018, Pisa, Italy*. Springer, 2020, pp. 188–194.

[6] D. Prattichizzo, M. Malvezzi, I. Hussain, and G. Salvietti, "The sixth-finger: a modular extra-finger to enhance human hand capabilities," in *The 23rd IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 993–998.

- [7] I. Hussain, G. Salvietti, M. Malvezzi, and D. Prattichizzo, "Design guidelines for a wearable robotic extra-finger," in *2015 IEEE 1st International Forum on Research and Technologies for Society and Industry Leveraging a better tomorrow (RTSI)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 54–60.
- [8] D. Prattichizzo, G. Salvietti, F. Chinello, and M. Malvezzi, "An object-based mapping algorithm to control wearable robotic extra-fingers," in *2014 IEEE/ASME International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 1563–1568.
- [9] G. Salvietti, I. Hussain, M. Malvezzi, and D. Prattichizzo, "Design of the passive joints of underactuated modular soft hands for fingertip trajectory tracking," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 2008–2015, 2017.
- [10] M. Malvezzi, Z. Iqbal, M. C. Valigi, M. Pozzi, D. Prattichizzo, and G. Salvietti, "Design of multiple wearable robotic extra fingers for human hand augmentation," *Robotics*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 102, 2019.
- [11] T. Lisini Baldi, N. D'Aurizio, S. Gurgone, D. Borzelli, A. d'Avella, and D. Prattichizzo, "Exploiting Intrinsic Kinematic Null Space for Supernumerary Robotic Limbs Control," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Robotics and Automation*, London, UK, 2023.
- [12] M. Dragusanu, Z. Iqbal, D. Prattichizzo, and M. Malvezzi, "Exploiting a wearable extra-finger for haptic applications," in *Haptics: Science, Technology, Applications: 13th International Conference on Human Haptic Sensing and Touch Enabled Computer Applications, EuroHaptics 2022, Hamburg, Germany, May 22-25, 2022, Proceedings*, vol. 13235. Springer Nature, 2022, p. 366.
- [13] I. Tursynbek, A. Niyetkaliye, and A. Shintemirov, "Computation of unique kinematic solutions of a spherical parallel manipulator with coaxial input shafts," in *2019 IEEE 15th International Conference on Automation Science and Engineering (CASE)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1524–1531.
- [14] C. M. Gosselin and E. Lavoie, "On the kinematic design of spherical three-degree-of-freedom parallel manipulators," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 394–402, 1993.